

SUPPLEMENT 4. Relevant Chinese scientific names in this study.

Scientific Names

Latin	Chinese
<i>Scleroderma</i>	硬皮马勃属
<i>Scleroderma</i> sect. <i>Caloderma</i>	硬皮马勃属棘皮硬皮马勃组
<i>Scleroderma</i> sect. <i>Reticulatae</i>	硬皮马勃属网孢硬皮马勃组
<i>Scleroderma</i> sect. <i>Sclerangium</i>	硬皮马勃属豆瓢硬皮马勃组
<i>Scleroderma</i> sect. <i>Scleroderma</i>	硬皮马勃属硬皮马勃组
<i>Scleroderma areolatum</i>	网隙硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma boluoshanense</i>	菠萝山硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma bovista</i>	大孢硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma capeverdeanum</i>	佛得角硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma cepa</i>	光硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma gaipeioides</i>	鸡腿形硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma lunare</i>	月球硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma nastii</i>	尼泊尔硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma navigatum</i>	航海硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma pernicococcum</i>	魔珠硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma plutonium</i>	冥王星硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma solare</i>	太阳硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma sutepense</i>	素贴山硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma venenatum</i>	毒硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma xanthochroum</i>	珍珠金硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma yunnanense</i>	云南硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma zengchengense</i>	增城硬皮马勃
<i>Scleroderma zijinshanense</i>	紫金山硬皮马勃